

MODIFICATION OF DROP WEIGHT METHOD FOR MEASURING SURFACE AND INTERFACIAL TENSION OF LIQUIDS

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The procedure and apparatus adopted by Harkins *et al.* have been used for the rapid and accurate determination of surface and interfacial tension of a number of liquids. The values obtained agree closely with those available in the literature.

In the drop weight method of Harkins *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 41, 499; 1916, 38, 228, 236, 242), the application of suction to the receiving vessel is inconvenient and the variation in liquid head lowers the drop size in the course of a determination. The apparatus and procedure described herein overcome these limitations.

EXPERIMENTAL

A capillary pipette, the details and dimensions of which are shown in Fig. 1(a), is constructed of a 2 mm I.D. straight pyrex tubing. The nozzle N is polished with a fine emery paper to get a sharp tip of circular cross section. The stop-cock S is located such that the test liquid does not come into contact with the stop-cock grease. The wooden board (on which a cm. graph paper is pasted) supports the pipette and enables it to be hooked from laboratory stands.

FIG. 1

FIG. 1 (a)

To determine the surface tension of a liquid, it is sucked into the clean dry pipette and the bottle 'B' is securely held in position. After allowing sufficient time for the liquid in the U bend to attain the temperature of the water-bath 'W', three or four drops are released from the tip very slowly by careful manipulation of the vacuum. Thus, the drops attain the temperature of the water-bath before reaching the nozzle tip. All the drops are released under the same liquid head. The volume of the drops released is taken from the change in meniscus in the calibrated horizontal section 'AD' as fluid displacement is independent of temperature.

In determining the interfacial tension between two liquids, the heavier liquid is taken into the pipette and the lighter liquid into the bottle. Alternatively, a pipette with the tip pointing upwards, as shown in Fig. 1(b), is used and is found to furnish good results.

From the average drop volume, the surface tension is determined by the equation

$$\sigma = \frac{V \rho g}{2 \pi r \psi} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

(where σ = surface tension in dynes/cm, V = volume of drop in c.c., ρ = density of liquids in g./c.c., g = acceleration due to gravity, 981 cm/sec², π = a const., 3.1416, r = radius to tips in cm and ψ = function of $r/V^{1/3}$) using the same correction factor ψ , as Harkins *et al.* (*loc. cit.*, 1919) since drops are formed under the same condition. For interfacial tension, $\Delta\rho$ is used in place of ρ in equation (1).

The surface and interfacial tension values of some organic liquids, determined at 20° using the apparatus and procedure described herein, are recorded in Tables I and II, along with the standard values reported in the International Critical Tables (Vol. IV, pp. 432-475). Table III shows the interfacial tension values of some liquids in contact with water at different temperatures. These tables and the surface tension values of some liquids, determined at different temperatures, show that the deviations are within the limits of experimental error.

TABLE I
Surface tension of liquids at 20°.

Liquid.	Density.	Surface tension.		% Dif.
		Found.	Lit.	
1. Acetylene tetrabromide	2.9630	49.76	49.67 ± 0.1	0.18
2. Benzene	0.8792	28.92	28.88 ± 0.05	0.14
3. CCl ₄	1.5910	26.67	26.77 ± 0.1	0.37
4. Chlorobenzene	1.1040	33.09	33.19 ± 0.1	0.30
5. Ethylene dibromide	2.1800	38.90	38.75 ± 0.1	0.39
6. n-Hexane	0.6814	18.65	18.43 ± 0.2	0.11*
7. Methyl-n-propyl ketone	0.8110	25.05	25.20 ± 0.5	0.60
8. Nitrobenzene	1.2040	43.98	43.90 ± 0.5	0.18
9. o-Nitrotoluene	1.1640	41.38	41.46 ± 0.2	0.04
10. m-Nitrotoluene	1.1570	40.76	40.90 ± 0.2	0.34
11. Toluene	0.8638	28.45	28.43 ± 0.05	0.07
12. Water	0.9983	72.90	72.75 ± 0.05	0.21

* The deviation is 0.11 % if literature value is taken as 18.63. If the mean value is taken as the basis, the deviation is 1.19%.

TABLE II

Interfacial tension of liquids in contact with water at 20°.
(Density of distilled water at 20° = 0.9982 g./c.c.).

Liquid.	Density.	Interfacial tension.		% Diff.
		Found.	Lit.	
1. Benzene	0.8792	34.86	35.00 ± 0.05	0.40
2. Bromoform	2.8710	40.70	40.85	0.37
3. CCl ₄	1.5910	45.15	45.00 ± 1.0	0.33
4. Chlorobenzene	1.1040	37.73	37.41	0.86
5. Ethyl ether	0.7145	10.92	10.70 ± 0.2	0.18*
6. Ethylene dibromide	2.1800	36.65	36.54	0.30
7. n-Hexane	0.6814	51.11	51.10	0.02
8. Methyl-n-propyl ketone	0.8110	6.215	6.28	1.04
9. Nitrobenzene	1.2040	25.80	25.66	0.55
10. o Nitrotoluene	1.1640	27.36	27.19	0.63
11. m-Nitrotoluene	1.1570	27.86	27.68	0.65
12. Toluene †	0.8606	36.09	36.10	0.03

* The deviation is 0.18% if literature value is taken as 10.90. If the mean value is taken as the basis, the deviation is 2.06%.

† For toluene, the values given are at 25°. Density of distilled water at 25° = 0.9971 g./c.c.

TABLE III

Interfacial tension of liquids in contact with water at diff. temp.

Liquid.	20°.	25°.	30°.	40°.	50°.
1. Benzene	34.86	34.65	34.48	34.07	33.52
2. CCl ₄	45.24	44.82	44.30	43.19	41.20
3. Chlorobenzene	37.73	36.86	36.17	35.28	34.36
4. Ethylene dibromide	36.65	36.08	35.41	34.22	33.12
5. Methyl-n-propyl ketone	6.215	6.805	5.93	5.701	5.45
6. Toluene	...	36.09	35.68	34.88	34.08

The pipette developed and herein described can be readily prepared and used for the rapid and accurate determination of surface and interfacial tensions of liquids.

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